

Alcrs: AI-Designed Anti-CRISPRs as Programmable CRISPR Inhibitors

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Specificity

Diversity
properties, substrate

Programmability

1 micron

CRISPR technologies : why the Off Switch Matters

Critical need for temporal and spatial control to minimize unintended consequences

Chloe Dawson/Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

CRISPR Clinical Trials: A 2025 Update
July 9, 2025 [Perspectives](#), by Hope Henderson

**Spatial and Temporal
Regulation**

CRISPR technologies : why the **Off Switch** Matters

Critical need for temporal and spatial control to minimize unintended consequences

Human health

Chloe Dawson/Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

Viral genome

Inhibition of gene drives

**Spatial and Temporal
Regulation**

✓ Specificity
 ✗ Rapid Response

Hadian-Jazi & Valentin-Alvarado et al.,
 Unpublished.

Article | [Open access](#) | Published: 11 July 2023
De novo design of protein structure and function with RFdiffusion
 Joseph L. Watson, David Juergens, Nathaniel R. Bennett, Brian L. Trippe, Jason Yin, Helen E. Eisenach, Woody Ahern, Andrew J. Borst, Robert J. Ragotte, Lukas F. Milles, Basile I. M. Wicky, Nikita Hanikel, Samuel J. Pellock, Alexis Courbet, William Sheffler, Jue Wang, Preetham Venkatesh, Isaac Sappington, Susana Vázquez Torres, Anna Lauko, Valentin De Bortoli, Emile Mathieu, Sergey Ovchinnikov, Regina Barzilay, ... David Baker [+ Show authors](#)
 Nature 620, 1089–1100 (2023) | [Cite this article](#)

Step 0

Visualise the entire catastrophe

Think ahead of time, about everything.....

Cas13 dynamics : **know** your protein of interest !

Critical need for thorough investigation

How well do I know my protein of interest ?

- Quality of the structure available
- Flexibility / dynamicity
- Binding Data

L. buccalis (Lbu) Cas13a

Binary → Ternary
PDB 5XWY → PDB 5XWP

Cas13 dynamics : **know** your protein of interest !

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How well do I know my protein of interest ?

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- Flexibility / dynamicity
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What is next ?

- Expression / Purification
- Pool Screen ?
- Assays

**Design (tag, how many)
Evaluate your designs
Properties of your binders**

Binary → Ternary
PDB 5XWY → PDB 5XWP

Step I

AI protein design (Binders)

Focus on RF-Diffusion strategy

AI-designed anti-CRISPRs (Alcrs)

De novo design of inhibitors against RNA-targeting CRISPR-Cas13

AI-designed anti-CRISPRs (Alcrs)

De novo design of inhibitors against RNA-targeting CRISPR-Cas13

In Silico Test phase

- Target
- Hotspots
- Pae Interaction score
- RMSD
- 200/500 designs

In Silico Production phase

- Thousands of designs
- Success rate
- Manual filtering
- Aromatics

Model:	S23TR24	OS:	Rocky 8
CPU	2x Intel Xeon Scalable Gold 5320 Processor 26-Core		
OS Disk	1 TB SSD		
Disk	4x 3.84TB SSD for Scratch		
Data	4x 22TB Enterprise HDD(SW RAID5)		
Memory	1 TB ECC Registered DDR4 DRAM		
GPU	4 x NVIDIA RTX 4090 24G GPUs		

2x Intel Xeon Scalable Gold 5320 Processor 26-Core, 2.2GHz
512 GB ECC Registered DDR4 DRAM
2x NVIDIA RTX A6000 Graphics Cards, 48GB GDDR6
1TB SSD for Boot
2x 3.84 TB NVme SSD for scratch
8 TB Enterprise SSD for AlphaFold2 and/or Rosetta Fold packages
4x 18 TB Enterprise HDD(SW RAID 5 (~54TB Raw after RAID))

AI-designed anti-CRISPRs (Alcrs)

De novo design of inhibitors against RNA-targeting CRISPR-Cas13

In Silico Test phase

- Target
- Hotspots
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In Silico Production phase

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Dec 2023

Jan 2024

Feb 2024

How does it work

Test phase

Production phase

96 Design

Wet Lab

5 tests
200 binders

4 hotspots (V, H, W)
70-100 / 100-130 residues
 α/β
5000 Binders x 2

Alcr designs are highly diverse

Designs share little to no structural or sequence similarity

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Step II

Screening process

Turning Designs into Data: A Medium-Throughput Approach

Tailoring throughput to fit your design and objectives

- 96 Clonal Genes
- Pet 29b(+)
- NGS verified
- ~3weeks

- Options for larger screen

Assaying Alcrs function as Cas13 inhibitors

Rapid scalable in vitro screening to benchmark activity

Expression & Purification

Step III
Alcrs Characterization

AlcrVIA1

AlcrVIA2

AlcrVIA3

Alcrs are robust & True to Design

Alcrs retains structure under heat and digestion

AlcrVIA1

Xray
AlphaFold

AlcrVIA2

Within Asymmetric Unit

AlcrVIA3

Inter-Asymmetric Units

Nathan Chai

Alcrs are precise regulation tools

Alcrs offer targeted and reliable control of LbuCas13a

Alcrs are true to design

AlcrVIA1 inhibits LbuCas13a via its active site

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Step IV Applications

What about in vivo & pre-clinical testing

Designs are functional *in cells*

Alcrs rescue phage infection as designed

Jovita D'Silva

Designs are functional *in cells*

Alcrs rescue phage infection as designed

Honglin Chen

Mohamed Fareh

What about pre-clinical studies ?

Where are we at ?

AI design &
lab screening

- Rapid
- Scalable
- Highly Targeted

Alcrs

- Potent
- Specific
- Robust
- True to design
- Work in Cell

MONASH PROTEIN DESIGN Node

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UoM PROTEIN DESIGN

Rhys Grinter
Lab Head

Janik Clement
Binder Design

Daniel Fox
Bacteriology/Design

CRISPR

*Taveneau et al, 2024
- BiorXiv*

Bacterial Growth Inhibitors

Fox et al, 2025 - Nat Comm

Affinity Reagents

GPCR Modulators

Toxins

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Macromolecular Crystallisation
Platform**

Alcra against Cas13

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Honglin Chen

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